

EWA-BELT

Linking East and West African farming systems experience
into a BELT of sustainable intensification

Use of neem seed oil as an environmentally safe bio-pesticide to manage pest damage in different crops

Practice Abstract n.2

Authors: Joseph Adjebeng Danquah (1), Deodatus Kiriba (2)

Authors' affiliation: (1) Council for Scientific and Industrial Research – Savanna Agricultural Research Institute, Ghana; (2) Tanzania Agricultural Research Institute, Tanzania.

The EWA-BELT Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under agreement No 862848

Use of neem seed oil as an environmentally safe bio-pesticide to manage pest damage in different crops

As part of the research on retrieving plant protection traditional knowledge, several EWA-BELT project partners are investigating the efficacy of plant protection agents in greenhouse or field trials. The use of neem seed oil (NSO), as an environmentally safe pesticide to mitigate fall armyworm damage in maize, was tested by CSIR-SARI in Ghana. About 100–150 mg of NSO was obtained by measuring 1 kg of neem seeds, removing debris and the external covering. The kernel was pounded into a fine paste and kneaded with cold water until the oil emerged, which was then collected with a foam material. A knapsack was first filled to half its capacity with water, followed by sequentially adding 10 ml of liquid soap, 25 ml of NSO, and again water up to 15 L, vigorously shaking with each addition to obtain a homogenous mixture. The first application was done when maize plants were 2–3 weeks old and the second at the 6th–7th week. A reduction in infestation and damage was observed, with a grain yield increase by over 40% compared to the untreated plants. Within the project, the partner KDC is also testing the NSO, produced by local women in Ghana, to manage pest infestation in cowpea. A ~70% yield increase was found compared to the untreated plots and ~10% compared to the use of another tested bio-pesticide: *Securidaca longipedunculata* root extract. Moreover, in Northern Tanzania TARI evaluated the efficacy of different doses (0.5FR, 1FR, 2FR and 4FR) of a homemade bio-pesticide [full rate (FR) = 0.5 kg of pepper (*Capsicum* sp.) + 3 kg *Tephrosia vogelii* (fish bean) + 1 kg Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) in 20 L water] in controlling field pests on lablab (*Lablab purpureus* (L.) Sweet) and common bean. This treatment allowed an increase in grain yield compared to the untreated plants, up to 2.6 times in common bean and 1.7 times in lablab, which was not significantly different from the use of a synthetic pesticide.

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Matumizi ya mafuta ya mbegu ya mwarobaini kama dawa salama kwa mazingira ili kudhibiti uharibifu wa wadudu katika mazao mbalimbali

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Matumizi ya mafuta ya mbegu za mwarobaini kama dawa salama kwa mazingira ili kudhibiti uharibifu wa wadudu katika mazao mbalimbali shambani kama sehemu ya utafiti wa kurejesha maarifa ya jadi ya ulinzi wa mimea, washirika kadhaa wa mradi wa EWA-BELT wanachunguza ufanisi wa kutumia mimea kudhibiti uharibifu wa wadudu mashambani. Matumizi ya mafuta ya mbegu za mwarobaini kama dawa salama kwa mazingira kupunguza uharibifu wa viwavijeshi kwenye mahindi, yalijaribiwa na Taasisi ya utafiti wa Kilimo kwenye ukanda wa savanna (CSIR-SARI) ya nchini Ghana. Ambapo takribani miligramu 100–150 za mafuta ya mbegu za mwarobaini zilizopatikana kwa kukamua kilogramu 1 ya mbegu za mwarobaini. Mafuta haya yalipuliziwa kwenye mimea yakichanganywa na sabuni miligramu 10 ya maji, mililita 25 za mafuta ya mbegu za mwarobaini kwenye bomba la lita 15. Jariribio la kwanza lilifanywa wakati mimea ya mahindi ikiwa na umri wa wiki 2–3, kupungua kwa uvamizi na uharibifu kulionekana na ongezeko la mavuno ya nafaka kwa zaidi ya 40% ikilinganishwa na mimea ambayo haikupuliziwa dawa hii ilionekana.

Pia ndani ya mradi huu washiriki wengine kutoka Taasisi ya maendeleo ya Kundok inchini Ghana (KDC) walitumia mafuta ya mbegu za mwarobaini yanayozalishwa na kikundi cha wanawake nchini Ghana, ili kuthiibiti uvamizi wa wadudu kwenye zao la kunde. Ambapo ongezeko la mavuno la 70% lilipatikana ikilinganishwa na mashamba ya zao la kunde ambayo hayakupuliziwa dawa hii, na 10% ikilinganishwa na matumizi ya dawa nyingine ya dukani au viwandani ya kuulia wadudu iliyojaribiwa.

Nchini Tanzania, taasisi ya Utafiti wa Kilimo Tanzania (TARI) ilifanya jaribio kutathimini ufanisi na ufanyaji kazi wa dozi mbalimbali za dawa asili ya mimea kwa ajili ya kuua visumbufu vya mazao shambani itokanayo na mchanganyiko wa pilipili kali iliyosagwa, utupa uliosagwa na mwarobaini uliosagwa na kuchanganywa katika lita ishirini za maji na hatimaye kutumika kudhibiti wadudu waharibifu kwenye zao la Ngwara na Maharagwe. Mchanganyiko huu ulipelekea ongezeko la mavuno mara 2.6 katika zao la maharagwe na mara 1.7 katika zao ngwara, ikilinganishwa na mimea ambayo haikupuliziwa dawa ya asili ya mimea, na ufanisi wa dawa hii ya asili ya mimea haukuwa tofauti sana na matumizi ya dawa ya wadudu ya viwandani iliyotumika.

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Nyimsi wala kpam zaŋ tuhi zunzuya barina kariwana ni

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Nyimsi wala kpam zaŋ tuhi zunzuya barina kariwana ni

Vihigu shɛya din niŋ zaŋ kpa baŋsim mini tuma shɛya din guri ka tayira binbira, EWA-BELT tuma bɛ taba vihirimi ni bɛ nya soya balibu shɛŋa dini gu ka tari binbira di zahimbu shee. Di balibu puuni, nyimsa wala kpam (NSO) tim tuhiri zunzuya (FAW) ka mali alaafɛe zaŋ ti ma daa nyɛla CSIR-SARI tum ayili nima ni daa zahim Ghana tingbani ni. Nyimsa wala kpam nyɛla bɛni daa doo shɛli. Bɛ daa zaŋla nyimsa kuruga pɛrigili (1kg) ka yihi di pɔyiri maa zaa. Nyimsa wole kpam daa nyɛla bɛni to shɛli ka zaŋ kom mahili n ŋmeli haali ka kpam ti yina. Bɛ zaŋla tani chee n zaŋ nyu kpam maa. Kamani 100–150mg kpam n daa yina. Kuruya pɛrigili (1kg) maa ni. Di yɛn tari kariwana ka chɛ zunzuya (FAW) yɔ, di yɛn le la din bahiri tim (knapsack) kom ka niŋ chibo kom bela (10ml) n pahi ka charisili haali ka di zaa ti gabi taba. Di nyaŋa, nyimsa wala kpam bela (25ml) daa boo pahi chibo kom maa ni ka lahi charisili viɛnyɛlinga. Kom daa lahi niŋ pahi ka di ti payi 15ml boobu la shee ka lahi charisili ka naan bahi kariwana maa. Tuuli bahi bu maa daa niŋ mi saha shɛli kariwana maa ni daa nyɛ bakoi ayi bee ata la ka bahibu din daa pahi ayi maa daa niŋmi dini daa payi bakoi ayobu zaŋ chaŋ bakoi ayopoin. Lala bahibu nima ŋɔ daa booi zunzuya maa barina nima ka che ka di niŋ yari vaabu pihinahi kɔbigu puuni (40%) zaŋ marisi din daa bɛ bahi maa. Di zuru nyimsi wole kpam bahibu buyi maa daa tuhi ka gu ka tari zunzuya (FAW) maa barina nima.

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